

ANCIENT ROMAN HISTORY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6595692>

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Annotation: *This article describes in detail the founding of Rome, governance in ancient Rome, the laws of the 12 tables, life in cities, the gods of the ancient Romans, and religious ceremonies.*

Key words: *plebeians, patricians, candidacy, dictator, consuls, people's tribune, veto, lecturers, mosaics, frisca, aqueduct, altar, pontiff, Vesta, augurs, vestals.*

Introduction: The Roman city began with agricultural settlements around the Tiber River. The small settlements around the Tiber River merged to form one large city. The city of Rome is located on seven hills. When the Tiber River overflowed, the area between the hills would become an impassable swamp. The location of the city was very convenient from a military point of view, the river and the swamp protected from the attacks of neighboring tribes of the Latins.

According to legend, the city of Rome was founded in 753 BC by the brothers Romulus and Remus. This date is considered to be the date of the founding of Rome. Babies were born in baskets and abandoned along the Tiber River. Along the Tiber River, the mother wolf finds them, sucks them and raises them. Then he finds a shepherd and raises his brothers. When they grow up, they decide to build a city around Tiber. The brothers then quarreled, and Romulus killed his brother Rem. Romulus gives the city its name. According to modern legends, the wolf that raised the brothers is a symbol of Rome.

Literature analysis and methodology: Rome becomes a large city and a fortress is built on the Capitol Hill to protect against enemies. The former Romans elected their own rulers, whose rulers were all military leaders, as well as judges and priests. A man nicknamed Magrur Tarkvini assassinated the country's elected ruler and seized power. Outraged by this, the people revolted and drove Tarquini out of the city. The population decides to move to a new form of government, which will not allow the whole community to be ruled by one person. Thus, the overthrow of the monarchy led to the creation of the Roman Republic, which in 509 BC was proclaimed the Roman Republic.

The Roman government convened a People's Assembly to solve important problems, and it would make peace, approve and repeal laws, declare war, and elect all important officials. All decisions of the Majlis were approved by the Senate, and

when the Senate was translated from Latin, the word "senate" meant "council of elders."

The Patricians were an indigenous people of Rome, and the people who immigrated to Rome were called the Plebeians. Those who could take part in the administration of Rome were only patricians. From the end of the 6th century BC, the Roman state came to be known as the Republic.

Results: The People's Assembly elected two governors from the patricians for a term of one year, and they were called consuls. The Senate consisted of 300 members. No law was passed by the House of Commons without discussion in the Senate. Wealthy people persuaded voters in various ways, organized free breakfasts, distributed various gifts, and so on. Wealthy people who nominated their candidates for the consulate on election day were dressed in white as "candida." The word "candidate", which means "candidate", is also derived from the word "candidate". The white silk robe on them said that both the candidate's conscience should be as pure as his robe. The consuls, who played an important role, were directly in charge of the state.

In ancient times, people with strong experience and respect played a key role in the Senate, but over time, consuls will take a seat in the Senate without any elections and will become its lifelong member, the senator. At the beginning of any war or uprising, the dictator and his deputy were appointed commanders-in-chief. The dictator had unlimited power. But he could not stay in power for more than six months.

Each consul was escorted by 12 security guards. The consul was able to punish the perpetrators, so he wore a string tied to the shoulders of the lecturers with an ax in the middle. The consuls consisted of two people, who had to discuss their main problems with each other. The consuls ruled the Roman republic for a year and tried the Romans, and during the war they commanded the army. Every year they reported to the People's Assembly.

Discussion: The People's Tribune was also established in the Roman Republic. The People's Tribune represented the interests of the poor Romans. They were elected at the meetings by an equal, transparent and secret ballot of all citizens. The people had to say the word "veto" in the tribune, otherwise the law would not have been passed.

Ancient Roman law was based on oral rules. In most courts, patricians who made unfair decisions often met. According to the laws of the plebeians, a council of ten patricians was formed, which was to make the laws mainly in writing. But the council was unable to complete the work. Then the Roman armies, mainly the plebeians, revolted. They go to the Holy Hill on the Roman coast and decide to build a new city with their own laws.

Thus, the laws engraved on 12 copper plates are placed in the Forum, the central square of Rome, for all to see. The patricians were thus forced to adopt a new law consisting of 12 tables. These laws declared private property inviolable,

but they mainly legitimized the inequality of plebeians and patricians. It was not until the beginning of the third century BC that all the inhabitants of Rome, regardless of status, passed laws that were considered equal before the law.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be noted that in everyday life, the Romans turned to their gods for help and patronage. Glorious temples were built for their gods. Many of the Roman gods were reminiscent of the Greek gods. Before they began their important work, they offered sacrifices to the Roman gods. According to them, different gods ruled different aspects of life. The Romans solved all the major problems by divination. Divination was performed with the help of priests, ie Avgurs.

As Rome's territory expanded, so did its cities. Roman cities were built on a plan that had already been perfectly produced. Many beautiful places in these cities were shopping malls, temples, baths, pharmacies, magnificent buildings. Most people lived in two- or three-story buildings. Wealthy people built houses for themselves. These houses had a central heating system: the floors were heated, and water flowed into the houses through pipes.

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